

INTRA-ARTICULAR ADMINISTRATION OF WHOLE BONE MARROW IN TREATMENT OF OSTEOARTHRITIS (OA) IN A SHEEP MODEL

Konstantin Aminkov

University of Forestry, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Sofia, Bulgaria

E-mail: kaminkov@ltu.bg

ABSTRACT

To investigate the therapeutic effect of whole bone marrow (WBM) in experimentally induced OA of the knee joint sheep.

OA of the knee joint was induced by removing of the medial meniscus of the joint. The first administration of 5 ml of autologous BM from the iliac crest was performed 12 weeks later; it was injected into the right knee. The second procedure was performed four weeks after the first one. The left knee joint was used as a control; 5 ml of saline solution was injected in it twice. The knee joints of both pelvic limbs were compared macroscopically and histologically; the dimensions of the lesions of the condyles of the femur, the amount and color of the synovial fluid and the degree of articular cartilage recovery were also examined.

The lesions in the condyles of the right knee joint were significantly smaller in size than those in the control joint. The amount of synovial fluid in the right knee was slightly more than the one in the left knee.

Injection of WBM in sheep with experimentally induced knee joint OA has a therapeutic effect.

Key words: Bone Marrow (BM), osteoarthritis (OA), treatment, sheep.

Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) is characterized by progressive and irreversible degeneration of articular cartilage. The capacity of the articular cartilage for restoration is weak due to the relative avascularity of the cartilage. Probably this is one of the main causes of ineffective treatment and recovery 19 J.D. Kim, et al., 2014; 20. C.J. Centeno, H. et al., 2015.

The structural changes seen in OA are a combination of cartilage thickness loss, periarticular bone formation (osteophytes, enthesophytes), subchondral sclerosis, cyst formation and changes in periarticular tissue.

The main goal of therapy in degenerative joint diseases is the application of therapeutic agents that stimulate the regenerative processes in the joint. The application of cell-based therapy is aimed at achieving this goal. Intra-articular introduction of whole bone marrow (WBM) has been implicated in degenerative joint disease. Aspirated BM is rich in transforming growth factor β (TGF- β), platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) (20 McCarrel T, and Fortier L2009, 18 Huang AH et al.). These growth factors are released from platelets and mesenchymal cells.

There is significantly increased research interest in the use of adult stem cells. Their use as cell-based therapy is related to their ability to differentiate into multiple cell subtypes (R. A. Hauser and E. Eteshola 2013).

The aim of the present study was to investigate histological changes in experimentally-induced OA on the basis of assessing the therapeutic effect of WBM when administered intraarticularly.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in 7 clinically healthy hoggets weighing 22–26 kg each. Prior to the study, all hoggets were deloused.

Anesthesia protocol:

All animals were premedicated with butorphanol tartrate (0.05–0.10 mg / kg) and diazepam (0.1–0.2 mg/kg) administered intravenously; an introduction into anesthesia was performed with a combination of ketamine hydrochloride (100 mg/ml) and diazepam (5 mg/ml) in doses of 0.5 ml/kg administered intravenously; the anesthesia was maintained by inhalation anesthetic with isoflurane (1.5%) and oxygen.

The right knee joint was accessed medially in aseptic conditions. After arthrotomy, 1/2 of the medial meniscus (cranial part) was removed. The joint capsule was restored by interrupted absorbable sutures gauge 2/0; the subcutaneous tissue was restored with uninterrupted absorbable mattress suture gauge 2/0; skin with interrupted nonabsorbable suture gauge 4/0. The same procedure was performed on the left knee, which is the control group. After a rest period of three weeks, all animals were forced to move on hard terrain for a distance of 90 meters. During the rest of the time, the animals moved freely.

BM extraction and introduction into the knee joint

The animal is placed in a lateral-lying position. After aseptic preparation of the area of the iliac crest, the area is numbed with 2–3 ml of 2% Lidocaine solution. A 1 cm incision on the skin on the iliac crest is made with scalpel with blade No. 15. A 10 ml syringe filled with 2 ml of heparin (1000/ml) is connected to the needle. The bone is injected with 1 ml of the syringe contents; after 1 minute the BM is aspirated. A total of 5 ml of bone marrow is aspirated from three sites.

5 ml of bone marrow is injected in the right knee joint (RJ); the same amount of saline solution is injected in the left knee (LJ).

Macroscopic examination

After 6 weeks all the sheep were euthanized. The macroscopic changes in knee joints were evaluated by two researchers independently of each other. The macroscopic findings were classified and scored in accordance with the International Cartilage Society (ICRS) cartilage repair evaluation system (16th Williams IR and Brophy RH, 2008).

Macroscopic scoring of cartilage (ICRS grading system)

Gross articular damage e score each area separately Score

Assessment of central cartilage of Medial femoral condyle, Trochlea, Medial tibial condyle

Normal	0
Surface roughening	1
Fibrillation and fissures	2
Small erosions down to subchondral bone (<5 mm diameter)	3

Larger erosions down to subchondral bone
(>5 mm diameter)

4

Histological analysis of bone and cartilage

The resulting samples were placed in a formalin solution, neutral buffered 10% as well as in the fixing mixtures of Carnua and Buen. Upon completion of their fixation, the samples were processed using classic histological methods. The paraffin-embedded histological sections were stained (5–7 µm thickness of the cuts made by Reichert microtome, Austria), with haematoxylin (Erich) -eosine, and then durable histological preparations were made (Vitanov, S. et al., 1995; Kiernan, JA, 2008). To ensure the quality of the applied histological methods, chemicals and reagents produced by Fluka and Merk were used.

Light microscopic examination was performed on durable histological preparations using a “Ergaval” light microscope (Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany). A universal light microscope NU – 2 (Carl Zeiss Jena, Germany) was used to study the microfiltration of the histological state in the investigated bioprojects, as well as the microscopic preservation of the histological findings.

Statistical analysis

All quantitative datasets are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to assess statistically significant differences between the groups. In cases where differences were statistically significant, the SNK-q test was performed for pairwise comparisons. Results were considered statistically significant at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Macroscopic findings

In all the joints treated with WBM, smaller lesions are found in the area of the medullary udder, the trochlear groove and the tibial plateau (Fig. 1). In the same areas of not treated joints, the lesions occupy broader surfaces and are deeper (Fig. 1). The cartilage destruction of the cartilage is most emphasized in the area of the trochlear groove.

According to the ICRS grading system, a lesions score between treated and non-treated joints in the areas of the medullary condyle (MC), the femoral sulcus (TS) and the tibial plateau (TP) were 2.3 ± 0.8 ; 2.3 ± 0.5 ; 1.4 ± 0.5 and respectively 3.3 ± 0.8 ; $3.2 \pm 0/1$ and 3.2 ± 0.4 (Fig. 2)

Right knee /Trochlear sulcus

Left knee /Trochlear sulcus

Right knee /Medial condyle/

Left knee /Medial

Right knee /Tibial plateau/

Left knee /Tibial plateau/

Figure 1: Macroscopic scoring of cartilage pathology in the trochlear sulcus, medial condyle and tibial plateau of sheep following induced OA.

Figure 2: The grading of the joints using the ICRS grading system.

Right knee (№ 3563)

Right knee (№3565)

Left knee (№ 3606)

Left knee ((№ 3607)

Figure 3: Histological Findings

Histological Findings

Right knee joint. In all histologically investigated preparations, the cartilage sample component is tightly bound to the already contained bone tissue component. Cellular composition is of sparsely located chondroblasts and single chondrocytes, a huge number of linearly ordered isogenic chondrocytes typical of cartilage tissue. Active cytophysiological processes are detected in the nucleus. The amorphous intracellular substance is soon synthesized and separated into the intercellular space (Fig. 3 (№ 3563 and №3565)). There are no areas of cartilage destruction.

Left knee joint. There is activated chondrogenesis. The cellular composition, its positioning in the cartilage and the state of the nuclear material repeat the described previously in the right knee (Fig. 3 (№ 3606)). Unlike the right knee joint, in the left knee joint, the zone of chondrogenesis, without a clear limit, it transitions into a zone of destruction of the newly created cartilaginous tissue and transformation into a bone (Fig. 3. (№ 3607)).

Discussion

Meniscus and cartilage tissue are known to have poor regenerative ability, requiring the use of new therapeutic strategies, including the use of MSC from different sources, capable of improving their internal healing potential (McCrum, CL, and Vangsness, CT, 2015 53. Then, J., et al., 2014).

A number of authors have found encouraging results in the use of MSC in the treatment of various musculoskeletal pathologies, including OA. Their healing effect depends on the procedure of isolating and increasing the cultures that affect, in turn, their phenotypic and clonogenic ability (J. Bara, J.J., et al., 2014; 42. Muraglia, A., et al., 2000).

To eliminate these requirements, many scientists apply direct implantation of the entire bone marrow niche, thus avoiding the changes associated with the cultivation of MSC (10. Veronesi, F., et al., 2013).

Data on the regeneration capabilities of WBM in various tissues, such as in the knee joint affected by OA, is scarce.

Abdel Hamid et al., 33 compare the therapeutic effects of WNM compared with that of bone marrow concentrate (BMC) administered intraarticularly in sheep with experimentally induced meniscus injury. The results show a slightly better therapeutic effect of WBM compared to that of BMC.

Fuat Duygulu et al., report a repair of a longitudinal tear throughout the width of the medullary meniscus, following an intra-articular administration of aspirate from autologous BM in sheep. This is confirmed by the formation of cartilage islets which are maintained by well-developed organelles and the presence of active chondroblasts, intensive synthesis of extracellular matrix and newly synthesized collagen fibrils.

The recovery potential of WBM has been assessed in view of their ability to inhibit the progression of inflammatory and degenerative processes in comparison to untreated joints.

Some authors demonstrate that growth factors play a crucial role in improving the recovery of meniscus (54. Delos, D., and Rodeo S.A., 2011).

Conclusion

The application of BM has a therapeutic effect on experimentally induced OA in the sheep. This is evidenced by the presence of discrete lesions in the area of the condyle of the treated limb.

It is expressed by the presence of less synovial fluid in the treated joints, a significantly lower number and significantly smaller lesions on the condyles of femor and the histologically proven presence of well-pronounced regeneration of the articular cartilage.

References

1. Aldini, N., and Fini, M. (2013). *Clinical use of bone marrow, bone marrow concentrate and expanded bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells in cartilage disease*. Stem Cells Dev, Vol. 22: 181.
2. Bara, J. J., Richards, R. G., Alini, M., and Stoddart, M. J. (2014). *Concise review: bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells change phenotype following in vitro culture: implications for basic research and the clinic*. Stem Cells, Vol. 32, 1713.
3. C. B. Little, M. M. Smith, M. A. Cake, R. A. Read, M. J. Murphy, F. P. Barry. (2010). *The OARSI histopathology initiative e recommendations for histological assessments of osteoarthritis in sheep and goats*. Osteoarthritis and Cartilage, Vol. 18: S80–S92
4. C. J. Centeno, H. Al-Sayegh, S. Goodyear, and M. D. Freeman. (2015). *A dose response analysis of a specific bone marrow concentrate treatment protocol for knee osteoarthritis*. BMC Musculoskelet Disord, Vol. 16: 258.
5. Delos, D., and Rodeo S. A. (2011). *Enhancing meniscal repair through biology: platelet-rich plasma as an alternative strategy*. Instr Course Lect, Vol. 60: 453.
6. Dimitrov, D. S. (2014). *Cytology, Histology and Embryology*. Stara Zagora, “Litera Print” Ltd, Stara Zagora, BG, pp. 122–125.
7. Eurell, J. A., B. L. Frappier. (2006). *Dellman,s Textbook of Veterinary Histology*. Sixth Edition, Blackwell Publishing, USA, pp. 31–61.
8. Hauser, R. A. and Eteshola E. (2013). *Rationale for Using Direct Bone Marrow Aspirate as a Proliferant for Regenerative Injection Therapy (Prolotherapy)*. The Open Open Stem Cell Journal, Vol. 4: 7–14.
9. Huang A. H., Motlekar N. A., Stein A., Diamond S. L., Shore E. M., Mauck R. L. (2008). *High-throughput screening for modulators of mesenchymal stem cell chondrogenesis*. Ann Biomed Eng, 36:1909–21.
10. J. D. Kim, G. W. Lee, G. H. Jung, C. K. Kim, T. Kim, J. H. Park et al. (2014). *Clinical outcome of autologous bone marrow aspirates concentrate (BMAC) injection in degenerative arthritis of the knee*. Eur J Orthop Surg Traumatol, Vol. 24:1505.
11. McCarrel T., Fortier L. (2009). *Temporal growth factor release from platelet-rich plasma, trehalose lyophilized platelets, and bone marrow aspirate and their effect on tendon and ligament gene expression*. J Orthop Res, Vol. 27: 1033–42.
12. McCrum, C. L., and Vangsness, C. T. (2015). *Postmeniscectomy meniscus growth with stem cells: where are we now?* Sports Med Arthrosc, Vol. 23: 139.
13. Muraglia, A., Cancedda, R., and Quarto, R. (2000). *Clonal mesenchymal progenitors from human bone marrow differentiate in vitro according to a hierarchical model*. J Cell Sci, Vol. 113: 1161.
14. Pak, J., Lee, J. H., and Lee, S. H. (2014). *Regenerative repair of damaged meniscus with autologous adipose tissue-derived stem cells*. Biomed Res Int, 436029.
15. Veronesi F., Giavaresi G., Tschon M., Borsari V., Nicoli A. N. and Fini M. (2013). *Clinical use of bone marrow, bone marrow concentrate, and expanded bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells in cartilage disease*. Stem Cells Dev, Vol. 22: 181–192.
16. Williams I. R. and Brophy R. H. (2008). *Cartilage repair procedures: clinical approach and decision making*. Instr Course Lect, Vol. 57: 553–561.